

Polydopamine-Coated Hexagonal Boron Nitride for Heat Dissipation Application

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Introduction

With the ongoing miniaturization of high-density electronic devices, the demand for high-performance thermally conductive materials for efficient heat management has grown increasingly critical [1]. Heat buildup in confined spaces can degrade performance, shorten device lifespan, and cause system failures, underscoring the importance of reliable thermal interface materials (TIMs) [2]. To improve the thermal conductivity of polymer-based composites, ceramic fillers are typically added. Among them, hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) is a promising candidate due to its platelet morphology, offering high in-plane thermal conductivity (up to 600 W/m·K), electrical insulation, and chemical stability [3]. However, anisotropic conductivity of hBN strongly depends on particle orientation; random dispersion disrupts thermal pathways and reduces efficiency [4]. In this study, a self-binding hBN structure was developed using polydopamine (PDA) as a binder. A well-aligned brick-and-mortar architecture was constructed without any polymer matrix by inducing direct bonding between hBN platelets. Uniform PDA coating and nanobumps (NBs) formation during polymerization promoted localized secondary aggregation and strong interfacial adhesion, enabling effective in-plane heat transfer.

Experiment

- Self-polymerization of DA occurred in a 150mM tris buffer solution.
- Extensive PDA coating on the hBN surface was induced by high concentrations of Tris buffer and DA.
- PDA-NB-hBN composites were fabricated via vacuum assisted filtration (VAF) followed by hot pressing.

Fig. 1. Fabrication of PDA-NB-hBN composites

Results & Discussion

Fig. 2. (a)-(c) Surface morphology of PDA coated hBN and (d) PDA induced NBs marked in red. (e) TGA graph of PDA coated hBN.

- Two-stage PDA deposition induced by controlled polymerization
- Uniform coating (PDA layer) → Localized aggregation (NBs)

Fig. 3. (a) Cross-sectional microstructure and (b) XRD pattern of PDA-NB-hBN.

- A well-aligned brick-and-mortar structure formed by self-bonding of PDA-coated hBN particles during VAF and hot pressing

Fig. 4. (a) Stress-strain curve, (b) tensile properties, (c) thermal conductivity and (d) thermal interfacial resistance (TIR) of PDA-NB-hBN composites.

Fig. 5 (a) Schematic of the thermal dissipation test, (b) thermocouple setup and (c) time-dependent temperature difference (ΔT) of the chip

Conclusions

- Extensive PDA coating containing NBs was polymerized on the surface of hBN particles, imparting self-binding characteristics to the material.
- PDA-NBs-hBN film exhibited a nacre-inspired brick-and-mortar architecture, in which hBN and PDA functioned as the brick and mortar, respectively.
- Without the use of external binders or polymer matrices, the film achieved mechanical stability with a tensile modulus of 9.59 MPa and a tensile strength of 8.65 MPa.
- Localized interfacial adhesion by PDA-NBs reduced thermal resistance, achieving multidirectional thermal conductivity of 4.82 W/mK in the k_L and 27.77 W/mK in the k_I.
- The film demonstrated practical heat dissipation performance as a TIM, by reducing the maximum operating temperature by approximately 3 °C.

Reference

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